

"YASHIL IQTISODIYOT VA TARAQQIYOT"

IV GLOBAL VA MILLIY IQTISODIYOT TRENDLARI: "O'ZBEKISTON - 2030" STRATEGIYASI

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2025

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MAXSUS SON

- MACROECONOMIC STABILITY
•LABOR MARKET IN THE GREEN ECONOMY
•GLOBAL ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL ECONOMIC RELATIONS
•GREEN INVESTMENT AND FINANCING
•GREEN TECHNOLOGIES
•ECO-TOURISM
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CONFERENCE "GLOBAL AND NATIONAL ECONOMIC TRENDS"

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2nd CONFERENCE ON BANKING / FINANCIAL DIRECTION OF THE PRIVATE SECTOR

2030

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**TOSHKENT DAVLAT
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(MAXSUS SON)

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08.00.13 Menejment
08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
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MUNDARIJA

INNOVATSION SIYOSATNI AMALGA OSHIRISHNING USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI – OLIY TA'LIM TRANSFORMATSIYASI, RAQAMLI MODERNIZATSIYA VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH OMILLARI.....	13
Sharipov Kongratbay Avezimbetovich	
O'ZBEKISTON YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISHI: ZARURAT, MAQSADI VA AYRIM MUAMMOLARI, YECHIMLAR	16
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna	
FAN, TA'LIM VA ISHLAB CHIQRISHDAGI SO'NGGI TENDENSIYALAR VA INNOVATSIYALAR	25
To'ychiyev Olimjon Alijonovich	
QURILISH TASHKILOTLARIDA KREDITGA LAYOQATLILIKNI BAHOLASHNI RAQAMLASHTIRISH	30
Mavlanov Normo'min Normamatovich	
BUDJET TASHKILOTLARIDA DAVLAT XARIDLARINI SAMARALI TASHKIL ETISHDA ELEKTRON SAVDOLARNING AHAMIYATI.....	37
Turabov Sarvar Abdumalikovich	
O'ZBEKISTONNI MINTAQAVIY TA'LIM VA ILM-FAN HABIGA AYLANTIRISHNING ISTIQBOLLI YO'NALISHLARI	41
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Maxamatjon o'g'li	
HUDUDIY RIVOJLANISH STRATEGIYALARIGA INNOVATSION KOMPONENTLARNI INTEGRATSIYA QILISH USULLARI	46
Muminov Fazliddin Xusniddin o'g'li	
OROL DENGIZI MEROSI: EKOLOGIK FOJIANI BARQAROR EKOTURIZM IMKONIYATLARIGA AYLANTIRISH	52
Zufarova Nozima	
KORXONALARNING YASHIL MARKETING STRATEGIYASINI ISHLAB CHIQISH METODOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	60
Ergashxodjayeva Shaxnoza Djasurovna	
O'ZBEKISTONDA ISHCHI KUCHI BOZORINING TAKRORIY AMAL QILISHINING NAZARIY JIHATLARI	66
Mamaraximov B.E.	
BANK-MOLIYA TIZIMIDA QIMMATLI QOG'OZLAR VA MOLIYAVIY INSTRUMENTLARDAN FOYDALANISH ORQALI GAROV DIVERSIFIKATSIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI.....	70
Xolbozorov Husniddin Norbek o'g'li	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA TO'QIMACHILIK SANOATIDA MARKETINGNING INNOVATSION KONSEPSIYALARI.....	76
Jumayev Olimjon Sadulloevich, Axmedova Shoxsanam Sindbod qizi	
SAVDO KORXONALARIDA EKOLOGIK MAHSULOTLARNI TARG'IB QILISH VA SOTISHNI RAG'BATLANTIRISH USULLARI	84
Jalalova Dildora Jamolovna	
DIRECTIONS OF FORMING AND PROVIDING A COMPETITIVE EXPORT-ORIENTED ECONOMY IN UZBEKISTAN	87
Asatullaev Khurshid Sunatullaevich, Nasirxodjaeva Dilafruz Sabitkhanovna, Abdullayeva Madina Kamilovna	
FROM SCIENCE TO BUSINESS: HOW UNIVERSITIES STIMULATE INNOVATION	94
Prof. A. Bobozhonov, Prof. A.M. Shatre, Assoc. Prof. V. Kirilova Vladimirova, prof. R.Kh. Karlibaeva	
PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF GREEN TECHNOLOGIES IN UZBEKISTAN BASED ON ADVANCED INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE	100
Otamuratov Sarvar	
SPECIFIC FEATURES OF MIGRATION FROM UZBEKISTAN AND PROSPECTS FOR ORGANIZATIONAL IMPROVEMENT	105
Sabiroya Lola Shavkatovna, Shaislamova Nargiza Kabilovna	

KORXONA BARQAROR AXBOROT TIZIMINI YARATISH QIYINCHILIKLARI.....	112
Abidov Abdujabbar Abduxamidovich	
TIJORAT BANKLARI FAOLIYATIGA FOIZ RISKINING TA'SIRI VA ILMIY-NAZARIY ASOSLARI.....	119
Isakov.J.Ya	
CREATION OF A MECHANISM FOR THE DEVELOPMENT AND INTRODUCTION OF A MODEL OF COMPLETE TRANSITION TO THE NETZERO ENERGY SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN	127
Makhmudova Guljakhon N., Gulomova Nigora Farxadovna	
УСИЛЕНИЕ ВОЗДЕЙСТВИЯ ХОЗЯЙСТВЕННОГО МЕХАНИЗМА НА СТОИМОСТНУЮ ОЦЕНКУ ОСНОВНЫХ ФАКТОРОВ ПРОИЗВОДСТВА.....	133
Алишер Расулев, Сергей Воронин	
РОЛЬ ФИНАНСОВОЙ ГЛОБАЛИЗАЦИИ В РАЗВИТИИ МАЛОГО И СРЕДНЕГО ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСТВА: ПЕРСПЕКТИВА И ПРИКЛАДНЫЕ РЕШЕНИЯ ДЛЯ ИХ ПЕРЕХОДА К МСФО.....	143
Эргашева Шахло Тургуновна	
DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS OF AGRICULTURAL ECONOMIC ACTIVITY UNDER DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION	151
Boburjon Vafoev	
ENERGETIKA TIZIMIDAGI KORXONALAR MOLIYAVIY HOLATINING TAHLILI.....	157
Matnazar Yusupovich Raximov	
АСПЕКТЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ РАЗВИТИЕМ ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО ТУРИЗМА В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ.....	162
Очилова Хилола Фармоновна	
TA'LIM XIZMATLARI BOZORINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLAR.....	167
Abdullayev Suyun Artikovich	
THE INTERCONNECTION BETWEEN DIGITAL LEARNING PLATFORMS AND THE DIGITAL ECONOMY.....	171
Kuchkarov Takhir Safarovich, Kholmonov Shodiyor Karshiboyevich	
BANK-MOLIYA TIZIMI VA XUSUSIY SEKTORNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA YANGI TEXNOLOGIYALAR YORDAMIDA BANK FAOLIYATINI RAQAMLASHTIRISH IMKONIYATLARI	174
Norov Akmal Ruzimamatovich	
РАЗВИТИЕ БАНКОВСКО-ФИНАНСОВОЙ СИСТЕМЫ И ЧАСТНОГО СЕКТОРА В РАМКАХ ПЕРСПЕКТИВ ВСТУПЛЕНИЯ ВО ВСЕМИРНУЮ ТОРГОВУЮ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЮ	180
У.А.Юлдашева	
ЗЕЛЕННЫЕ ПОТРЕБИТЕЛИ - ПУТИ РАЗВИТИЯ ЗЕЛЕННОГО РОСТА В РАМКАХ УСТОЙЧИВОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ	185
Дехканова Наргиза Шарифовна	
ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИЙ АУДИТ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	192
Ходжаева М.Х.	
TADBIRKORLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA AHOLINING MOLIYAVIY SAVODXONLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI.....	199
Akbarova Barno Shuxratovna	
SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC GROWTH THROUGH TOURISM UNDER THE GREEN ECONOMY FRAMEWORK	204
Jumayev Akbar Mahmudovich	
МАКРОИQTISODIY BARQARORLIKNI TA'MINLASHDA BANK TIZIMINI RIVOJLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	210
Erkinxojiyev Ismoiljon Ikromjon o'g'li	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA MINTAQAVIY SANOAT KORXONALARIDA KORPORATIV MADANIYATNI RIVOJLANTIRISH VA BOSHQARUV SAMARADORLIGINI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH.....	216
Matrizayeva Dilaram Yusupbayevna	
UZBEKISTAN AT THE CROSSROADS OF HISTORY AND GREEN INNOVATION: FROM THE GREAT SILK ROAD TO A SUSTAINABLE FUTURE	220
Avalova Gulshod Murodullayevna	

ГЛАВНЫЕ ВЕКТОРЫ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОЙ ПОЛИТИКИ ПО ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЮ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	226
Абдуллаева М.К.	
ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT IN THE INDUSTRIAL CLUSTERS SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN: MODERN TRENDS AND DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS.....	233
Kholikova Rukhsora Sanjarovna	
HUDUDDAGI KICHIK BIZNESNING SAMARALI TARKIBIY TUZILMASINI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA MUTASSADI TASHKILOTLARNING O'ZARO UYG'UN HARAKATINI TASHKIL ETISH.....	239
Sharipov Kuvondik Baxtiyorovich	
BUSINESS ANALYTICS IN HISTORICAL PERSPECTIVE: LESSONS FROM THE INDUSTRIAL REVOLUTION TO THE DIGITAL AGE	246
Burhanova Sabo Tulanovna	
"COST ENGINEERING"NING NAZARIY ASOSLARI VA UNI IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIKNI OSHIRISHDAGI O'RNI.....	252
Zaynitdinova Umida Djalalovna	
FEATURES AND WAYS OF FURTHER DEVELOPMENT OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY.....	256
Kobilov Alisher, Majidova Irodahon	
ПИЩЕВАЯ ИНДУСТРИЯ УЗБЕКИСТАНА: АГРАРНЫЙ ИМПУЛЬС, ЭНЕРГЕТИЧЕСКОЕ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЕ И ЦЕНОВАЯ КОНЪЮНКТУРА.....	263
Юлдашев Голибжон Тургунович, Элдорбеков Гофурбек Искандарбек угли	
INCOME INEQUALITY AND MACROECONOMIC DETERMINANTS IN UZBEKISTAN: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS	273
Muhammad Eid Balbaa, Marina Sagatovna Abdurashidova	
РЫНОК ТРУДА В УСЛОВИЯХ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ЗЕЛЕННОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	276
Амирджанова Ситора Суннат кизи	
EKOLOGIK QO'RIQXONALARDA MONITORING JARAYONLARINING IQTISODIY VA TASHKILIY ANAMIYATI.....	282
Homidov Hamdam Hasan o'g'li	
ГАРМОНИЗАЦИЯ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ СТАНДАРТОВ БУХГАЛТЕРСКОГО УЧЕТА В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН В СООТВЕТСТВИИ С МСФО	288
Абдужалилова Дилноз Абдусаттаровна	
SUSTAINABLE TOURISM AND BIODIVERSITY PROTECTION: CASE OF UZBEKISTAN WITHIN THE UNESCO WORLD HERITAGE FRAMEWORK.....	294
Yuldasheva Dilnoza Ulugbekovna	
ПРАКТИЧЕСКОЕ ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ НЕЙРОМАРКЕТИНГА НА МАРКЕТПЛЕЙСАХ (WILDBERRIES, UZUM MARKET, ЯНДЕКС МАРКЕТ)	300
Юлдашев Жамшид Абрарович	
ЗЕЛЕНАЯ ЭКОНОМИКА КАК СТИМУЛ РАЗВИТИЯ РЫНКА ТРУДА УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	309
Шаюсупова Наргиза Тургуновна	
GLOBALLASHUV SHAROITIDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANISHI O'ZBEKISTONNING XALQARO SAVDOSIGA VA IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGIGA TAHDID SIFATIDA.....	315
Mamatov Mamajan Ahmadjonovich	
SUG'URTA TASHKILOTLARI FAOLIYATI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH VA INNOVATSION SUG'URTA MAHSULOTLARINI JORIY QILISH MASALALARI	321
Xalikulova Gulzada Tadjimuratovna	
O'ZBEKISTON OZIQ-OVQAT BOZORIDA YASHIL MARKETING STRATEGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH ORQALI BARQAROR ISTE'MOLNI RAG'BATLANTIRISH	333
Eshmatov Sanjar Azimqulovich	
ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ЗЕЛЁНЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ В РАЗНЫХ ОТРАСЛЯХ ЭКОНОМИКИ: ГЛОБАЛЬНЫЙ ОПЫТ И НАЦИОНАЛЬНАЯ ПРАКТИКА	337
Назарова Ра'но Рустамовна, Мусаева Гавхар Ахматжон кизи	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTDA MEHNAT BOZORI: O'ZBEKISTON TAJRIBASI VA ISTIQBOLLARI.....	343
Homidjonov Fozilxon Umarxon o'g'li, Haydarov Kamoliddin Baratovich	

GREEN INVESTMENT: PATHWAYS TOWARD A SUSTAINABLE FUTURE.....	348
Odilova Sitora Sayfitdin kizi	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA O'ZBEKISTON SANOAT KORXONALARIDA MARKETING STRATEGIYALARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	351
Kutbitdinova Mohigul Inoyatovna	
QURILISH MATERIALLARI SANOATIDA YASHIL TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYANING BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHGA TA'SIRI	356
Metyakubov Azamat Djumanazarovich	
ELEKTR SANOAT KORXONALARINING IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA MARKETING VOSITALARIDAN FOYDALANISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	361
Tursunxo'jayev Sardor Jamoliddin o'g'li	
УЧЕТ ЗАТРАТ И МЕТОДЫ ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЯ СЕБЕСТОИМОСТИ ПРОДУКЦИИ В НЕФТЕГАЗОВОЙ ОТРАСЛИ	368
Махкамова Саида Гайратовна	
MILLIY HISOBLAR TIZIMIDA INTELLEKTUAL MULK MAHSULOTLARINI MAKROIQTISODIY DARAJADA HISOBGA OLISHNING METODOLOGIK ASOSI.....	375
Sunnatov Muxtor Ne'matovich	
RENEWABLE ENERGY AND MACROECONOMIC STABILITY IN CENTRAL ASIA: PATHWAYS WITHIN THE GREEN ECONOMY	382
Khabibullo Abdullaev	
JAHON SUG'URTA AMALIYOTI ASOSIDA O'ZBEKISTON SUG'URTA BOZORIDA YANGI RIVOJLANISH YO'NALISHLARI.....	387
Abdimovminova Saodat Taxirjonovna	
INTEGRATING DATA SCIENCE INTO GREEN FINANCING AND ECO-INNOVATIONS: ACHIEVING THE GOALS OF UZBEKISTAN-2030	397
Norboev Odil Abraevich, Kungratov Ilmurod Kuzibay ugli	
O'ZBEKISTONDA SANOAT ISHLAB CHIQRISHINI DIVERSIFIKATSIYALASH AMALIYOTI VA ISTIQBOLLARI	404
Olimov Maqsudjon Komiljon o'g'li	
СОЗДАНИЕ ЗЕЛЕННОГО ЭНЕРГЕТИЧЕСКОГО КОРИДОРА В ЕВРОПУ: РЕГИОНАЛЬНЫЙ ПОТЕНЦИАЛ АЗЕРБАЙДЖАНА, КАЗАХСТАНА И УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	411
Лала Гамидова Адиль, Арзуман Гусейнов Айдын	
MAHALLA TIZIMIDA AHOLINI OZIQ-OVQAT MAHSULOTLARIGA BO'LGAN ISTE'MOL TALABLARI MODEL.....	419
S. Qulmatova	
AHOLI ICHKI MIGRATSIYASINING MEHNAT BOZORIGA TA'SIRINI STATISTIK O'RGANISH	427
Mirolimov Mirislom Mirshokir o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTONDA BANK TIZIMINI RAQAMLASHTIRISH TENDENSIYALARI VA MUAMMOLARI	434
Jumaniyozova Mukaddas Yuldashevna	
ЗЕЛЁНЫЕ ФИНАНСЫ: ГЛОБАЛЬНЫЕ ТРЕНДЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	438
Фаттахова Муниса	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI SOHASI FAOLIYATINI DAVLAT TOMONIDAN MUVOFIQLASHTIRISH VA BOSHQARISH MEKANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	444
Tuxtamishev Shodimurod Qurbonboyevich	
MARKETING TADQIQOTLARI ASOSIDA MEVA-SABZAVOT MAHSULOTLARI EKSPORT SALONIYATINI OSHIRISH	452
Xojiyev Elshod Yoqub o'g'li	
СПОСОБЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ НАУЧНЫМИ УЧРЕЖДЕНИЯМИ В ЦЕЛЯХ ПЕРЕХОДА НА РАЗРАБОТКУ ЗЕЛЕННЫХ ИННОВАЦИЙ	459
Юдаков Александр Андреевич	
O'ZBEKISTONNI JAHON SAVDO TASHKILOTIGA A'ZO BO'LISHINING OZIQ-OVQAT XAVFSIZLIGINI TA'MINLASHGA TA'SIRI.....	466
Axmedova N.A.	

O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA KLASTERLAR FAOLIYATINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING IQTISODIY MEKANIZMI	471
<i>Sherkulov Shohruh Erkin o'g'li</i>	
DEVELOPMENT SCENARIOS OF UZBEKISTAN'S ACTIVE LABOR FORCE UNTIL 2030 AND THEIR ECONOMIC IMPLICATIONS.....	476
<i>Ganiev Bakhtiyor Zulfikor ugli, Rakhmonov Bekzod Sharibjon ugli</i>	
РАЗВИТИЕ ЗЕЛЁНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ КАК ФАКТОР СТИМУЛИРОВАНИЯ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ АКТИВНОСТИ ЖЕНЩИН В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	481
<i>Дониерова Фотимабону Алишер кизи</i>	
YASHIL ENERGETIKA VA UNING IQTISODIY TARAQQIYOTDAGI O'RNI	488
<i>Babadjanova Malika Ruzimova</i>	
BENCHMARKING IN THE AUTOMOTIVE INDUSTRY: STRATEGIES FOR SUSTAINABLE COMPETITIVENESS	492
<i>Abdurashidova Nigora</i>	
УЗБЕКИСТАН СТРЕМИТСЯ К УСТОЙЧИВОМУ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОМУ РОСТУ, ВНЕДРЯЯ ПРИНЦИПЫ «ЗЕЛЁНОЙ» ЭКОНОМИКИ	498
<i>Сагдуллаева Гулнора Ботыровна</i>	
O'ZBEKISTONDA FAOLIYAT YURITAYOTGAN KOMPANIYALARNING GLOBAL MARKETING STRATEGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH YO'NALISHLARI.....	502
<i>Sharipov Ixtiyor Baxtiyorovich</i>	
ZAIF BANDLIKDAN UNUMLI BANDLIK SARI TRANSFORMATSIYA: O'ZINI O'ZI BAND QILISH	507
<i>Qurbonov Samandar Pulatovich</i>	
ВОЗОБНОВЛЯЕМАЯ ЭНЕРГИЯ В ГЛОБАЛЬНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКЕ: ТЕКУЩИЕ ТЕНДЕНЦИИ И БУДУЩЕЕ РАЗВИТИЕ.....	514
<i>Меҳрибан Самедова Тофик</i>	
RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNING MEHNAT UNUMDORLIGINI OSHIRISHGA TA'SIRI	521
<i>Zafar Alisherovich Mamadiev, Nodira Isametdinovna Xasanxonova</i>	
SAVDO KORXONALARIDA BUXGALTERIYA HISOBINI XALQARO STANDARTLARGA INTEGRATSIYA QILISH MEKANIZMLARI.....	526
<i>Ablazov Lazizbek Abdiquosimovich</i>	
TIJORAT BANKLARINING TRANSFORMATSIYASI JARAYONINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	530
<i>Ziyadullaev Z.</i>	
TO'LOV TIZIMI KONSEPTUAL MODELINING SHAKLLANISH TAMOYILLARI	537
<i>Toshniyozov Sherali Kamoliddinovich</i>	
STAFF PERFORMANCE EVALUATION BASED ON KPI SYSTEM INDICATORS.....	546
<i>Rakhmatullaeva Shakhnoza Khamidovna, Sadriddinova Sevinchkhon</i>	
SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT AND THE TRANSITION TO A GREEN ECONOMY IN THE CONTEXT OF GLOBAL ECONOMIC TRENDS	555
<i>Svetlana Yurievna Shatokhina</i>	
MILLIY TARBIYA OMILLARI VA MILLIY MADANIY YONDASHUV ASOSIDA TALABALARDA O'QUV TASHABBUSKORLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING NAZARIY-AMALIY ASOSLARI.....	560
<i>Azimova Nilufar Nuriddinovna</i>	
TIJORAT BANKLARI TOMONIDAN KICHIK BIZNES SUBYEKTLARINI TA'MINLASHDA BANK RESURSLARINING ROLI	567
<i>Xodjayeva Jeyrona Ravshonbek qizi</i>	
O'QUV DASTURINI INTEGRATSIYALASH VA YASHIL KO'NIKMALARNI RIVOJLANTIRISH: AKADEMIK VA SANOAT O'RTASIDAGI TAFOVUTNI YOPISH	572
<i>Qo'ziqulova Dilfuzaxon Maxammatisaqovna</i>	
DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION AND DIGITAL PLATFORMS AS A KEY FACTOR IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESS ENTITIES	580
<i>Rizayeva Nilufar Oblakulovna</i>	

IQTISODIY OLIY TA'LIMDA STRATEGIK INNOVATSIYALAR: YASHIL KO'NIKMALARNI MILLIY VA GLOBAL BARQARORLIK MAQSADLARI BILAN MUVOFIQLASHTIRISH	585
<i>Xasanova Zarina Maxamadaliyeva</i>	
MARKAZIY OSIYODA YASHIL IQTISODIYOT: BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH YO'LIDAGI TO'SIQLAR VA ISTIQBOLLAR.....	594
<i>Aminov Shovkat O'ktam o'g'li</i>	
ПЕСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ЗЕЛЁНЫХ ОБЛИГАЦИЙ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	598
<i>Саидахмедова Аида Мирзаевна</i>	
ПОВЫШЕНИЕ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ И СНИЖЕНИЕ РИСКОВ КОММЕРЧЕСКИХ БАНКОВ НА ОСНОВЕ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ ТРАНЗАКЦИЙ В ФИНАНСОВЫХ ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫХ СИСТЕМАХ С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ СИММЕТРИЧНЫХ КРИПТОСИСТЕМ.....	605
<i>Раҳимбердиев Қ.Б.</i>	
ИНТЕГРАЦИЯ ФИНАНСОВЫХ И СТРАХОВЫХ ИНСТРУМЕНТОВ ДЛЯ СТИМУЛИРОВАНИЯ УСТОЙЧИВОГО ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РОСТА	612
<i>Ш.Ф.Кобилжонова</i>	
СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ КАПИТАЛА ХОЗЯЙСТВУЮЩИХ СУБЪЕКТОВ В КОНТЕКСТЕ РАЗВИТИЯ БАНКОВСКО-ФИНАНСОВОЙ СИСТЕМЫ И ЧАСТНОГО СЕКТОРА ЭКОНОМИКИ	618
<i>Д.А.Юлдашева</i>	
РОЛЬ БАНКОВСКО-ФИНАНСОВОЙ СИСТЕМЫ И СТРАХОВЫХ МЕХАНИЗМОВ В СТИМУЛИРОВАНИИ РАЗВИТИЯ ЧАСТНОГО СЕКТОРА	624
<i>Г.Т.Ахмедова</i>	
SUG'URTA BOZORI FAOLIYATINI RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA TRANSFORMATSIYALASH VA UNING RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISH MASALALARI.....	630
<i>Saidov Farrux Faxriddinovich</i>	
OPPORTUNITIES TO ENSURE SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC GROWTH IN THE ENERGY SECTOR THROUGH THE TRANSITION TO A GREEN ECONOMY.....	635
<i>Ulashov Aliboy Rashid ugli, Istamova Nasiba Narzillo kizi</i>	
INKLYUZIV OLIY TA'LIMDA MUSTAQIL ISHLASH JARAYONINI TASHKILLASHTIRISH.....	641
<i>Akbarova Kamola Abdujabbor qizi</i>	
YOUTH-DRIVEN PATHWAYS TO GREEN EMPLOYMENT: A THEORETICAL EXAMINATION OF INCLUSIVE ECONOMIC STRATEGIES	646
<i>Suvpulatov Ozodjon Alijon ugli</i>	
KICHIK BIZNES INFRATUZILMASINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA XORIJIY TAJRIBALAR VA UNING O'ZBEKISTON UCHUN AHAMIYATI	651
<i>Botirova Xulkar Olimjonovna</i>	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH KLASTERLARI: NAZARIY ASOSLAR VA AMALIY YONDASHUVLAR.....	655
<i>Sherkulova Nodirabegim Baxordin qizi</i>	
BIOTECHNOLOGICAL SOLUTIONS IN URBAN PLANNING: OPPORTUNITIES AND LIMITATIONS OF "LIQUID TREES"	660
<i>Nosirkulov Asadjon Ahmadjon ugli</i>	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA TIKLANADIGAN ENERGIYA MANBALARINING O'RNI.....	663
<i>Fayziyeva Dilso'z Bahodirovna</i>	
KREDIT PORTFELIDA MUAMMOLI KREDITLAR ULUSHINI KAMAYTIRISH YO'LLARI	668
<i>Salixova G.J</i>	
O'ZBEKISTONDA KANDOLAT MAHSULOTLARI BOZORINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA YASHIL MARKETING STRATEGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH.....	672
<i>Boboyorova Maftuna Xaqqul qizi, Boboyorov Islombek Xaqqul o'g'li</i>	
OLIJ TA'LIM TIZIMIDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNI QO'LLASH METODLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	675
<i>Xusniddinov Yorqinjon Muhiddin o'g'li</i>	

MODA SANOATIDA CRM TIZIMLARINI ELEKTRON SAVDO PLATFORMALARI BILAN UYG'UNLASHTIRISHDAGI TO'SIQLAR	679
Xalilova Nafisa Komilovna	
ENHANCING FOREIGN ECONOMIC RELATIONS AS A DRIVING FACTOR IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE NATIONAL ECONOMY	683
Khaitova Feruza Bahrom kizi	
MARKAZIY OSIYO MAMLAKATLARIDA XORIJIY INVESTITSIYALARNING QAYTA TIKLANUVCHI ENERGIYA MANBALARIGA TA'SIRI	687
Akishova Shaxnoza Davlet qizi	
BUXORO VILOYATIDA HUNARMANDCHILIK FAOLIYATINING RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYALARI: TAHLIL VA ISTIQBOLLAR.....	693
Ravshanova Gulchexra Ravshanovna	
SANOATNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING MEKANIZMLARI TURLARI VA OLIMLARNING YONDASHUVLARI	698
Ne'matov Shoxruxbek Ma'murjon o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTON BANK-MOLIYA TIZIMIDA KREDIT RISKLARINI BOSHQARISH AMALIYOTINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH VA UNING XUSUSIY SEKTOR RIVOJLANISHIGA TA'SIRI.....	703
Norova Nozima Nabiyevna	
O'ZBEKISTON BANK-MOLIYA TIZIMIDA REAL SEKTORNI KREDITLASH MEKANIZMLARINI SAMARALI JORIY ETISH VA XUSUSIY SEKTOR RIVOJIGA TA'SIRI.....	709
Abduxomidov Ikromjon Maxamadin o'g'li	
MOLIYA TIZIMIDA BOJ-TARIF SIYOSATINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH VA XUSUSIY SEKTOR RIVOJLANISHIGA TA'SIRI (OZIQ-OVQAT IMPORTI MISOLIDA).....	715
Rizaev Mirmahmud Xotamjanovich	
YASHIL MARKETING VA ESG INTEGRATSIYASI: STATISTIK TAHLIL VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI	721
Charos G'ayratova	
ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ НАПРАВЛЕНИЯ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОГО КАПИТАЛА ДЛЯ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ УСТОЙЧИВОГО ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РОСТА В УСЛОВИЯХ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ «ЗЕЛЁНОЙ» ЭКОНОМИКИ.....	727
Г.А.Хайитбаева	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISH SHAROITIDA TIJORAT BANKLAR TOMONIDAN TADBIRKORLIK FAOLIYATINI KREDITLASH.....	734
Tajiddinov Jamshiddin Shamsutdinovich	
IQTISODIYOTNING TARKIBIY TRANSFORMATSIYASIGA XORIJIY INVESTITSIYALAR TA'SIRINI BAHOLASH MEKANIZMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	738
Shodiboyeva Dilzoda Farhodjon qizi	
MOLIYA TIZIMI BARQARORLIGI VA BUDJET TUSHUMLARINI OSHIRISHDA TASHQI IQTISODIY FAOLIYATNING AHAMIYATI.....	743
Aktamov Akbarjon Aslan o'g'li	
ENSURING SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC GROWTH IN THE TRANSITION TO A GREEN ECONOMY: AN ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CARBON EMISSIONS AND ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT.....	748
Shakhriddinova Sitara Tolibjon kizi	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISH JARAYONIDA TIJORAT BANKLARIDA INVESTITSIYA LOYIHALARI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA ESG TAMOYILLARINING ROLI	760
Ostonaqulova Gulchehraxon Muhammadyoqub qizi	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT TAMOYILLARI ASOSIDA SANOAT KORXONALARIDA YETKAZIB BERISH STRATEGIYALARINI ISHLAB CHIQISH	769
Yusupov Ulug'bek Mamayusupovich	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT KONTEKSTIDA MAKROIQTISODIY BARQARORLIKNI MUSTAHKAMLASH: XALQARO TAJRIBA VA O'ZBEKISTON AMALIYOTI.....	776
Isroilov Islomiddin Kamoliddin o'g'li	

RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA SHAROITIDA SPORT TASHKILOTLARINING YANGI BIZNES MODELLARINI ISHLAB CHIQISH	782
G'ulomov Musirmon	
O'ZBEKISTONDA IQTISODIYOTGA XORIJIY INVESTISIYALARNI JALB ETISHNING USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI VA ISTIQBOLLARI	786
Sharipova Shahnoza Baxtiyorovna	
O'ZBEKISTONDA INVESTISIYA MUHITIGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR VA INVESTISIYALARNING IQTISODIYOTGA JALB ETILISH HOLATI TAHLILI	795
Karimova Qunduz Atanazarovna	
O'ZBEKISTON TURISTIK XIZMATLAR BOZORIDA BANDLIK TRANSFORMATSIYASINI VA UNI TARTIBGA SOLISH HOLATINI TAHLIL QILISH	804
To'xtayeva Xurshida Farxodovna	
INVESTITSIYA LOYIHALARIGA TA'SIR QILUVCHI INVESTITSIYA RISKLARINI BAHOLASH.....	811
Zohidova Ruksora Komiljon qizi	
ТИПЫ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ ФИНАНСОВЫХ РАЗВЕДОК: ОСНОВНЫЕ РАЗЛИЧИЯ, ФОРМЫ И МЕТОДЫ ОСУЩЕСТВЛЕНИЯ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ.....	817
Эсанов Шохрух Отабекович	
FACE RECOGNITION PROGRAM IN PYTHON.....	823
Khurramova Maftunakhon Zhurabekovna, Khurramov Azizjon Bakhodir ugli	
FORMATION OF ACCOUNTING POLICY FOR INTANGIBLE ASSETS.....	827
Farxod T. Abdvaxidov, Ramazon A. Abdurakhmanov	
O'ZBEKISTON EKSPORT TARKIBINI YUQORI QO'SHIMCHA QIYMATLI MAHSULOTLARGA O'TKAZISH STRATEGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	834
Raximov Eshmurod Normuradovich	
EKSPORT FAOLIYATIDA ERKIN IQTISODIY ZONALARNING SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI.....	838
Berdivaliyeva Madina Komiljon qizi	
TURIZM KLASTERLARIDA TIBBIY XIZMATLAR INTEGRATSIYASI: XALQARO TAJRIBA VA O'ZBEKISTON AMALIYOTI	841
Yazdanova Shohista Tuyg'un qizi Farxodova Shohnoza Umidbek qizi	
O'ZBEKISTON HAVO TRANSPORTI TIZIMINING JAHON IQTISODIYOTIDAGI O'RNI VA RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	850
Azimova Moxinur Nozimovna	

CREATION OF A MECHANISM FOR THE DEVELOPMENT AND INTRODUCTION OF A MODEL OF COMPLETE TRANSITION TO THE NETZERO ENERGY SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: Effective implementation of the tasks set in the framework of the "World Government Summit-2022" held in Dubai and the 24th goal of the "Development Strategy of the New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" of the Republic of Uzbekistan to provide the economy with continuous electricity and to apply "Green economy" technologies to all sectors active implementation, increasing the energy efficiency of the economy by 20 percent. Currently, in our country, there is no mechanism and methodology for implementation of issues such as transition to a green economy, thereby saving electricity and reducing factors that have a negative impact on the environment at the local level. In particular, the lack of knowledge and skills of local state authorities and civil servants working in neighborhoods and residents about the NetZero energy system weakens the possibility of effective implementation of the tasks specified in the above documents. Therefore, to create a methodology for developing a strategy for the transition of neighborhoods to the NetZero energy system; analyze their economic and legal basis and develop proposals for its improvement; the tasks of developing a mechanism for forming the population's culture about the NetZero energy system are defined.

Key words: Green energy, NetZero energy, system, energy, decarbonization, digitization, alternative energy, green economy, local government.

Annotatsiya: Dubay shahrida o'tkazilgan "World Government Summit-2022" sammiti doirasida belgilangan vazifalar hamda O'zbekiston Respublikasining 2022–2026 yillarga mo'ljallangan "Yangi O'zbekiston taraqqiyot strategiyasi"ning 24-maqjadi — iqtisodiyotni uzluksiz elektr energiyasi bilan ta'minlash va barcha sohalarga "yashil iqtisodiyot" texnologiyalarini joriy etish orqali iqtisodiyot energiya samaradorligini 20 foizga oshirish — samarali amalga oshirilishi talab etilmoqda. Hozirgi kunda mamlakatimizda yashil iqtisodiyotga o'tish, elektr energiyasini tejash va atrof-muhitga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatuvchi omillarni mahalliy darajada kamaytirish kabi masalalarni amalga oshirish mexanizmi va metodologiyasi mavjud emas. Xususan, mahallalarda faoliyat yuritayotgan davlat organlari va xodimlar hamda aholining NetZero energiya tizimi bo'yicha bilim va ko'nikmalarining yetarli emasligi yuqorida ko'rsatilgan vazifalarning samarali ijrosini zaiflashtirmoqda. Shu sababli, mahallalarning NetZero energiya tizimiga o'tishi bo'yicha strategiya ishlab chiqish metodologiyasini yaratish; uning iqtisodiy-huquqiy asoslarini tahlil qilish va takomillashtirish bo'yicha takliflar ishlab chiqish; aholining NetZero energiya tizimiga oid madaniyatini shakllantirish mexanizmini yaratish vazifalari belgilangan.

Kalit so'zlar: Yashil energiya, NetZero energiya, tizim, energiya, dekarbonizatsiya, raqamlashtirish, muqobil energiya, yashil iqtisodiyot, mahalliy boshqaruv.

Аннотация: Эффективная реализация задач, поставленных в рамках «World Government Summit-2022», прошедшего в Дубае, а также 24-й цели «Стратегии развития Нового Узбекистана на 2022–2026 годы» — обеспечение экономики бесперебойным электроснабжением и внедрение технологий «зелёной экономики» во все сферы с повышением энергоэффективности экономики на 20 процентов — остаётся приоритетной задачей. В настоящее время в стране отсутствуют механизм и методология для решения таких вопросов, как переход к зелёной экономике, экономия электроэнергии и снижение факторов негативного воздействия на окружающую среду на местном уровне. В частности, недостаточные знания и навыки местных государственных органов, служащих махаллей и населения по системе NetZero снижают возможность эффективной реализации указанных задач. Поэтому определены следующие задачи: создание методологии разработки стратегии перехода махаллей к системе NetZero; анализ её экономико-правовой основы и разработка предложений по её совершенствованию; разработка механизма формирования культуры населения по вопросам системы NetZero.

Ключевые слова: Зелёная энергия, NetZero энергия, система, энергия, декарбонизация, цифровизация, альтернативная энергия, зелёная экономика, местное управление.

INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, the global community has placed particular emphasis on achieving NetZero energy systems as a central priority in sustainable development. The experiences of the United States, Japan, France, Germany, South Korea, and China demonstrate that institutional transformation of the national economy through medium- and long-term models plays a decisive role in reducing carbon dioxide emissions and increasing energy efficiency. Over the past 10–15 years, the United States has achieved significant results in energy conservation, reducing total energy consumption by nearly 20 percent through targeted saving measures. This was largely the outcome of intensive scientific research on energy-saving technologies, the timely adoption of regulatory frameworks, and the introduction of innovative solutions. For example, since 1997, the Million Solar Roofs program has successfully installed solar systems on more than one million homes by 2010.

Similarly, Germany has introduced policies allowing private investors to install solar panels on roofs of public buildings covering more than 100,000 square meters, with generated electricity supplied directly into the urban grid. These global practices highlight the importance of combining legal support, financial incentives, and technological innovation in fostering NetZero transitions.

Building upon the contributions of scholars such as M. Baird, A. Carlson, A. Chetfield, S. Reddick, G. Feldhof, T. Kretzman, and McKnight, the current study emphasizes the relevance of local governance. Considering the specific role of the neighborhood institution in Uzbekistan, the research focuses on adapting global best practices to national conditions by developing mechanisms to strengthen the capacity of local authorities and residents for implementing NetZero systems.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The transition to NetZero energy systems has been a central topic of global scientific debate in recent years. Davis et al. [1] emphasized that achieving net-zero emissions requires profound changes in the structure of energy systems, including large-scale deployment of renewable energy and carbon capture technologies. Similarly, Azevedo et al. [2] argue that while significant progress has been made in understanding pathways to NetZero, many uncertainties remain regarding economic feasibility and technological scalability. DeAngelo et al. [3] further highlight that scenarios leading to zero CO₂ emissions must account for systemic interdependencies between energy, land, and water resources.

At the methodological level, Pye et al. [4] note that modelling NetZero systems demands a paradigm shift, moving beyond traditional optimization approaches towards integrated frameworks that account for uncertainty and socio-economic factors. Complementing this, Tsiropoulos et al. [5] examine European Union strategies, showing that achieving NetZero by 2050 requires aggressive investment in renewable energy, digital infrastructure, and policy reforms.

From a national perspective, Uzbek scholars such as Makhmudova, Ashurov, and Razakova [6] underline the role of digital ecosystems and platforms in supporting green transformation. Likewise, Makhmudova, Ashurov, and Gulomova [7] analyze the challenges of digital transformation in Uzbekistan’s economy, stressing the need for technological innovation and institutional reforms to accelerate sustainable NetZero pathways.

METHODOLOGY

This study applies a comparative and systematic approach to design a model for the full transition to a NetZero energy system in Uzbekistan. First, international experiences from the USA, Germany, Japan, South Korea, and the EU were examined through content analysis of policy documents, energy programs, and scholarly works. Second, economic and legal frameworks in Uzbekistan were analyzed to identify institutional gaps in implementing green energy reforms. A mixed-method strategy was adopted: qualitative analysis to evaluate policy consistency and governance mechanisms, and quantitative assessment using energy efficiency indicators and CO₂ reduction trends. Additionally, expert interviews with local government officials and residents were proposed to determine awareness levels, ensuring that the model reflects both global best practices and national realities.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The comparative study of global experiences demonstrates that the successful transition to NetZero energy systems requires long-term institutional transformation, strong legal frameworks, and sustained investment in innovative technologies. In the United States, over the last 10–15 years, energy consumption has been reduced by nearly 20 percent, largely due to the implementation of energy-saving programs and the adoption of advanced technologies. A notable example is the Million Solar Roofs initiative, launched in 1997, which by 2010

had installed solar systems on more than one million residential buildings, significantly expanding decentralized renewable generation.

Germany provides another valuable case, where policies enabled private investors to install solar panels on more than 100,000 m² of public building roofs and supply electricity directly to the city grid. These measures illustrate the effectiveness of integrating private sector participation into national energy strategies.

The works of Baird, Carlson, Chetfield, Reddick, Feldhof, Kretzman, and McKnight provide further scientific justification for focusing on both technological and governance dimensions of NetZero systems. Their findings underline the importance of embedding green energy policies at the lowest levels of governance.

For Uzbekistan, the neighborhood (mahalla) institution represents a unique platform for localizing NetZero strategies. By adapting international best practices to the socio-economic and legal context of Uzbekistan, it becomes possible to design a model that combines global scientific achievements with local institutional capacities, ensuring effective implementation of sustainable energy transitions.

Figure 1. Total renewable energy in selected countries share in energy supply, 2019

Since 1973, along with the development of energy saving measures, active work on the development of solar energy has begun in Japan. At that time, 1 watt of energy produced by a solar cell cost 30,000 yen. By 2000, this figure had decreased to 140 yen. Such a level of prices makes it reasonable to use solar panels in everyday life. By the end of 1997, solar panels had been installed on 8,000 residential buildings, with the government paying one-third of the battery installation costs. By the end of 2010, solar panels were installed on 1 million residential buildings. In 1979, the Energy Conservation Act came into force in Japan. It belongs to large industrial enterprises, which then accounted for 70% of the energy consumed. In Japan, a specific school of green energy development has been created, which are environmental management, social capital and institutional capacity theory of environmental management. The scientific research works of representatives of this school K. Abe, M. Taguchi, T. Saito, N. Mishima, M. Motosu, Y. Maruyama and Y. Himiyama were studied and the aspects of their achievements implemented in practice were thoroughly analyzed. It was found that mainly in Japan, more attention is paid to the interaction between the scientific research structures of the development of green energy and the public authorities, including the local government.

In Uzbekistan, there are the following scientific problems that need to be solved in this field:

1. In our country, there is no methodology of a mechanism for the transition to a green economy, thereby saving electricity and identifying factors that have a negative impact on the environment and reducing its impact at the neighborhood level;

2. Indicators for determining the qualification requirements and competencies of local government bodies and civil servants operating in the neighborhoods for the implementation of the NetZero energy system have not been developed, and there are no educational programs and special courses for improving their knowledge and skills in this direction;

3. The effect of the full transition to the NetZero energy system and global carbon dioxide reduction goals on the national economy by 2050 has not been analyzed by correlation-regression, and no econometric models have been developed in this regard;

4. There is no mid- to long-term model for a complete transition to the NetZero energy system;

5. The economic and legal basis of the transition to the NetZero energy system in the neighborhoods have not been sufficiently scientifically analyzed together;

6. The methodology of the system and mechanism of forming the culture of the population about the NetZero energy system has not been developed.

According to statistics, the demand for electricity in our country is predicted to grow by 6-7% per year until 2030, and the existing capacities do not allow to fully satisfy the domestic needs. It can also be observed that in the last 5 years, the volume of electricity production in Uzbekistan has increased from 61 billion kWh to 72 billion kWh or 1.2 times. Despite the reports made in this area, due to the existence of problems related to the supply infrastructure, in 2021, the unsatisfied demand for electricity in the republic amounted to 2-3 billion kWh. This increases the need for step-by-step reform of the energy resources market aimed at ensuring the participation of private investments in the country's continuous and full supply of energy resources.

If the share of renewable energy resources is about 20% in European countries, this indicator is much lower in Uzbekistan, and most of the electricity is produced in thermal power plants. 12-15 percent of the country's natural gas is wasted for their continuous operation. According to estimates, it is predicted that the volume of natural gas production will decrease significantly in the next 15-20 years. Diversification of electricity sources will help to get out of this situation.

Systematic and comparative economic- legal analysis in the project , complex approach, sociological surveys, systematic analysis , induction, deduction, logic, observation, statistical and research scientific abstraction, empirical, descriptive statistics, analysis and synthesis, econometric analysis, correlation-regression analysis, expert assessment, grouping, dynamic analysis, cluster used research methods such as method, complex approach. Experiences of foreign countries, including the USA, Japan, China, European countries, and the Republic of Korea, have been studied within the scope of the topic.

The scientific novelty of the research is the creation of a scientifically based mechanism for the implementation of the NetZero energy system in the neighborhoods based on the successful experiences of foreign countries, taking into account the uniqueness of the neighborhood institution in Uzbekistan. It is intended to obtain the following results:

1. As part of the international events of the «World Governments Summit-2022», priority global calls and forecast models expected in the world economy in the near, medium and long future (perspective) will be deeply analyzed, and opportunities will be determined for its implementation in the conditions of Uzbekistan;

2. A methodology for developing a strategy for transferring neighborhoods to the NetZero energy system will be created. The economic and legal basis of introducing the NetZero energy system in each neighborhood in the conditions of the Republic of Uzbekistan will be researched, and scientifically based proposals will be developed to increase the efficiency of electricity by 20%;

3. The influence of the population's culture about the NetZero energy system on the development of the green economy in the neighborhood will be scientifically studied and a scientifically based methodology will be developed;

4. Foreign experience aimed at increasing the share of alternative energy sources is analyzed and alternative energy programs for neighborhoods are proposed based on it;

5. Within the framework of the project, a scientific practical manual on the topics «Strategy of transfer to the NetZero energy system in neighborhoods», «Mechanism of transfer to the NetZero energy system in neighborhoods», «Mechanisms of raising the culture of the population about the NetZero energy system» and an educational practical manual on the topic «NetZero energy system» will be prepared;

6. On the basis of artificial intelligence, software will be created that evaluates the possibilities of implementing the NetZero energy system in the region and defines the main directions of implementation;

7. Software will be created to determine the rating of implementation of the NetZero energy system in the neighborhoods;

8. By introducing artificial intelligence, based on econometric analysis, a program will be created that identifies green entrepreneurship directions and mechanisms for its implementation in neighborhoods;

9. Equipment and software for determining air pollution and energy consumption will be created in neighborhoods;

10. The economic efficiency of the implementation of the NetZero energy system in the neighborhoods will increase up to 20 percent;

11. Household energy costs are saved;

12. In places, especially in rural households, the demand for energy resources is fully met;

13. It has a positive effect on the continuous supply of the population's demand for electricity in rural areas;

14. Alternative energy producing cooperatives will be established on the basis of public and private partnerships, which will create an opportunity for the state to continuously supply households with electricity;

15. The population's culture of NetZero energy system and efficient use of green energy is formed;

16. Economic indicators determining the introduction of the NetZero energy system in the regions and methods of rating them will be developed;

17. The methodology of creating cooperatives that produce alternative energy is offered to the neighborhoods and practical support is provided for the establishment of the center in exchange for a share in the cooperatives.

Table 1. Increasing the production capacity of Uzbekistan until 2030 indicators on

Indicator	Make a forecast release power increase (MW)					Electricity work release percentage (%)	
						2018	2030
	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023-30		
General	1 074.1	886.8	1 961.5	2 061.6	14 017.8	100	100
Traditional energy	1 050	1 807	1 777	2 259.4	10 910.2	90	75
Including power output	-	1 060	320	740	4 280	-	-
Total again renewable energy sources	24.1	119.8	504.5	542.2	7 387.6	10	25
- Hydropower	24.1	119.8	204.5	42.2	1 487.6	10	11.2
- Solar energy	-	-	300	400	4 300	-	8.8
- Wind energy	-	-	-	100	1 600	-	5

The result of the commercialization of the research results is seen in the following:

On the basis of the created methodology and software, services for the development of a strategy for the implementation of the NetZero energy system are offered for each neighborhood based on its characteristics. The use of this strategy provides an opportunity to reduce electricity consumption by 30-50% by introducing the NetZero energy system in neighborhoods. This service will be provided on a contractual basis in the future.

Training programs will be developed on the topics of «Strategy of transition to the NetZero energy system in neighborhoods», «Mechanism of transition to the NetZero energy system in neighborhoods», «Mechanisms for raising the culture of the population about the NetZero energy system» and «NetZero energy system», and based on them, about 50 thousand civil servants will be trained training courses are offered on the basis of a contract. An online training platform will be created on the above topics and will be offered on a paid basis for relevant industry representatives.

The methodology of creating cooperatives that produce alternative energy is offered to the neighborhoods and practical support is provided for the establishment of the center in exchange for a share in the cooperatives.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The analysis of international experiences and Uzbekistan's current energy situation demonstrates that the full transition to a NetZero energy system requires a comprehensive and step-by-step approach. Countries such as the United States, Germany, and Japan have shown that combining scientific research, supportive legislation, and financial incentives creates strong foundations for energy transformation. Their achievements underline the importance of linking innovation with active participation of local governments and private investors. In the case of Uzbekistan, the mahalla (neighborhood) institution offers a unique platform to localize NetZero initiatives, ensuring that reforms are adapted to socio-economic and cultural realities.

The study highlights several challenges: the absence of a national methodology for NetZero transition, insufficient qualification standards for local authorities, and the lack of econometric models to assess economic impacts. Moreover, the growing electricity demand, projected to rise by 6–7% annually, further increases the urgency of reform.

To address these issues, the following recommendations are proposed: develop a unified methodology for implementing NetZero at the neighborhood level; introduce specialized training programs to improve the skills of 50,000 civil servants; foster public–private partnerships for renewable energy cooperatives; and establish digital platforms with AI-based software to monitor emissions and energy efficiency. These steps will not only increase energy efficiency by up to 20 percent but also strengthen green entrepreneurship, reduce household costs, and ensure sustainable energy security for Uzbekistan by 2050.

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